

Do We Listen to Our Students?

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Abstract

This article reports on findings of Erasmus+ project Pythagoras aimed at investigating the impact of active teaching/learning methods on the knowledge acquisition in basic courses of mathematics at the engineering study programmes. Presented analysis of the feedback received from the international groups of students who tested prepared learning materials reveals their opinion on the 5 tested learning scenarios: escape room activity, mini-PBL, eduScrum, gamification, and stack exercises. Comments from students serve as a source of inspiration for development of appropriate teaching/learning methods reflecting students' primary needs and requirements.

Introduction

One of the main reasons for a high drop-out rate in the first year of engineering study programmes seems to be problems with passing exams in the basic courses of Mathematics. This is due to a lack of student engagement, various personal issues, and even high demands based on required deeper learning outcomes, see in Kayoko (2022). The Erasmus+ project, Pythagoras, strives to develop approaches that will make learning Mathematics more inclusive, efficient, enjoyable and real; connecting Mathematics teaching with real life cases linked to the students' fields of study. All project outcomes and activities are tailored to address the needs of the partner institutions in order to strengthen knowledge acquisition in the fundamental mathematics background. The results are checked from a variety of perspectives: mathematical content, mathematical processes, views about the nature of mathematics, and personal opinion of students regarding their learning preferences, as suggested in O'Leary (2023).

One of the project activities was a Summer School for Students, organised as Learning-Teaching-Activity lasting 5 days. Groups of 4 students from all 7 partner institutions attended the event and tested 5 different learning scenarios applied in teaching basic courses of mathematics in university bachelor study programmes. Learning activities were prepared by teams of mathematics teachers from the partner universities: Lucian Blaga University in Sibiu, Romania as project coordinator, Aalborg University in Denmark, The Hellenic Mediterranean University in Chania, Crete, Greece, The Porto Polytechnic in Oporto, Portugal, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, The University of La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain and Karlstad University, Sweden. A different didactic approach and active learning method were tested each day, while authors of each activity were responsible for the day's program and its evaluation. Students answered the prepared feedback questionnaires after each of the activities, where they stated their opinions on the presented didactic scenario. They were also asked to express their personal views on each particular method with respect to its impact on their knowledge acquisition, along with ideas for possible improvements from the learners' perspective.

Method of Investigation

Students worked in groups of 4 on solving particular tasks. Groups were sometimes mixed, formed of students from different countries, sometimes these groups represented a particular university and country. After completing the required tasks and delivering results, each activity was followed by an on-line questionnaire available for students to fill out individually. The feedback survey consisted of several general questions with a choice of answers, open questions to give opinions on the tested didactic method, and some questions about expected knowledge gain and efficiency of the learning process under this particular teaching/learning scenario. Questionnaires were anonymous, students were registered only by the country of their origin, and answers in all five surveys were analysed generally, with respect to the best and most favourite method from the student perspective. All questionnaires were prepared as on-line applications accessible using a unique QR code. Students were asked to express their opinions openly and honestly, with the declared intention that their views will be taken into account for development of new educational activities meeting their needs and expectations. The aim was to receive fresh ideas from those actors of educational process, who are mostly playing a passive role as recipients of new knowledge without the opportunity to comment on ineffective methods. Such methods are used in goodwill as a way to try to promote active learning, enhance curiosity in learning mathematics and support deeper conceptual understanding of students. The approach of all students during these activities was more positive than expected. They were keen on testing various ways of teaching/learning, eager to solve the assigned tasks, and very competitive, struggling to receive the best results in several scheduled games, quizzes and in team work on small projects that were carefully planned and prepared as computer applications, on-line games and spreadsheets or available as paper work in handed out packages. The teachers who authored the tested materials presented a short introduction at the beginning of lesson, with instructions on how to use a particular computer programme, application, ready-made applet, or provided paper sheets. They watched the engagement of students during the work, their interest and cooperation and social behaviour. All were ready to help students with possible problems that might occur during their work with presented materials due to different cultural, historical or other restrictions of particular country backgrounds and traditions in dealing with basic mathematical concepts and their symbolic representation. A summary of the feedback analysis is presented separately for each of the 5 active learning/teaching methods. Overall satisfaction with the event activities during all days is presented on the diagram from Pythagoras project report by Luntraru (2024) in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall satisfaction with the event activities

Digital Escape Room

The first day activity was work in small groups of 4 students, mixed or from the same university according to their own decision. Many students preferred to be in a mixed group in order to start international cooperation which they found as one of the added values and the most important benefit received from participation at this event. Groups received access to a newly designed computer application – an on-line digital escape room with special mathematical problems that had to be solved in order to get out. Partial solutions of small problems allowed players to continue through 3 rooms with additional pieces of information leading to final solution of the slightly more complex problem. The environment was designed to be a virtual 3D space with objects in the rooms, doors opened on inserting correct answers and codes, which was quite demanding on the quality of computers, necessitating longer processing time caused by many active players at the same time, and the response speed of the internet connection. Students were interested in using this game, but a bit disappointed by technical constraints. Some of the tasks were based on manual skills with playing games, e.g. quick fetching and moving some objects in the virtual scene, which were not related to any mathematical knowledge or task, but quite significantly influenced the score and results. Some students did not fulfil the final mathematical task in the third room, as they were not able to get access to this last room and stayed without reaching any mathematical problem, information or knowledge. Their disappointment was also reflected in the mostly negative attitude expressed in this day questionnaire answers. Dissatisfaction stemmed from design issues within the escape room application, which hindered its effective execution. Students articulated these concerns in their feedback, highlighting the technical challenges they encountered and how these problems detracted from their overall experience during that particular session. Some of the comments: *“The Escape room didn't have a way to escape :(”*. *“The first day's virtual escape room failed when it came to not crashing, not bugging, and enunciating the problems correctly. Otherwise, it would have been very interesting”*.

Mini PBL

The next activity was adapted PBL - Problem Based Learning method, in the form of miniPBL. Groups of students were asked to work on solutions of small problems related to some environmental issues. The task was to understand the applied problem described in a short introduction, to develop mathematical model of this problem and to find its

optimised solution, while the theoretical result had to be interpreted back to the practical solution of the applied problem. This approach was highly appreciated by students, who were interested in finding solutions of the real problems. They very much valued the fact that mathematics might help to model real life situations and to suggest their possible solutions with available optimisations. The feedback from students on this activity received in the evaluation questionnaire was overwhelmingly positive. A significant majority of participants reported that the sessions were well organized and met their expectations, reflecting a high level of satisfaction with the content delivered, as seen on diagram in Figure 2, from the Pythagoras project report by Luntraru (2024). A substantial portion of the respondents also indicated that the duration of the sessions was appropriate, the instructors effectively encouraged questions and fostered discussions among group members during the work on problems. This engagement is crucial for deepening understanding and enhancing the overall learning experience, suggesting that this activity supported the active participation and dialogue among students.

Figure 2. Analysis of answers in questionnaire on miniPBL activities.

EduScrum Method and Pre-Calculus Course

Two activities were planned for the third day. In the morning session the eduScrum activity was implemented, which was highly regarded and considered the highlight of the week. This method was marked by all students as the most suitable and relevant with respect to knowledge gain and satisfaction with the learning outcomes. Students worked in groups as national teams solving provided sprints that are sets of 5 problems related to Calculus I and II. Four problems were traditional tasks testing calculation skills and understanding of basic concepts from this topic, and the fifth one was an applied problem related to environmental issues to be solved by optimisation. Team members chose a leader – the scrum master, who guided the team work, distributed problems to team members and submitted collected solutions. Working achievements of all teams were assessed, and the best teams with the highest point score were awarded small prizes. All students were satisfied with the work in small teams and they appreciated the possibility to discuss problems together and share the workload. They also pointed to the social aspects of the team-work, working at their own pace, discussing misunderstandings

among team members, and share responsibility for the sprint tasks as a team. Almost all students considered this learning/teaching method to be most rewarding with respect to their personal knowledge gain and depth of achieved understanding.

The feedback on the afternoon Pre-Calculus course session was less favourable. Students commented on the inconsistency in teaching approaches during the afternoon session, stating, *"If one teacher tells us that teachers shouldn't teach while facing the board, then why does the next teacher do that?"* This highlights a perceived contradiction in teaching methods and suggests that greater consistency might enhance student engagement. Overall, less than half of the students who responded to the questionnaire felt that the day's sessions were well organized and their duration was appropriate, the sessions met their expectations and that the teachers effectively encouraged their engagement.

Figure 3. Analysis of answers in questionnaire on the third day activities.

Gamification

The activity for the day four was gamification, a learning method aiming to test acquired knowledge in basic mathematics. Students, in small 4-member teams, solved several problems presented as games. Points were awarded for correct answers, final points scores were declared after each game and winners received small prizes. This activity - learning, repeating and revising by playing, was regarded as interesting and efficient for fostering team cooperation and rewarding individual achievements in a pleasant, relaxing atmosphere. All students confirmed that the sessions were well organized and met their expectations. They also commended the teacher for his proactive attitude in encouraging questions and facilitating discussions. Students also gave positive remarks, as *"Very interesting topic, excellent presentation, engaging activities, and fun examples."* and *"The interaction with students and competitive games really encouraged teamwork."* This activity proved to be the most relaxing and valuable in terms of deepening knowledge and understanding, and particularly for the transfer of this knowledge to another context. Diagram with feedback results is in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Analysis of answers in questionnaire on the gamification activity.

Stack Exercises

On the last day of the event, Stack exercises were introduced as the learning activity. The students' task was to solve several problems presented in the Moodle environment as an exercise, in step-by-step mode. Comments were given to partial solution and any incomplete answers followed by hints that aimed to help solver to find the right procedure or to use the correct formula. References to textbooks or other digital study materials were provided to solver, who could find basic theoretical information in case if necessary, and repeat the topic. The opinion of students on this learning activity was very positive, most of them found this approach to be helpful and instructive. A few students did not like this approach. They criticised the fact that one could come to a correct solution without any knowledge gain, just following the given instructions. The majority of participants affirmed that the session met their expectations, highlighted its effectiveness in delivering the intended content, and the lead teachers' efforts in fostering an environment conducive to active participation. This feedback reflects a strong endorsement of the instructors' ability to engage students effectively and facilitate interaction throughout the educational session. The activity was regarded as the most suitable for individual study approach.

Figure 5. Analysis of answers in questionnaire on the Stack exercise activity.

Conclusions for Education

No teaching/learning method could be declared as the most effective one. Each method has its role and place in education and should be used carefully with a strategic plan taking seriously into consideration needs and expectations of students. EduScrum is the most appealing one to students, engaging their interest for the teamwork and share of responsibility, not neglecting the social aspects of this kind of cooperation.

We should listen to our students.

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